

AN INVERSE ESTIMATION OF HIGH STRAIN RATE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL CONSTITUENTS

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ABSTRACT

An inverse procedure which uses numerical optimization and a micro scale finite element model has been developed for estimation of high strain rate properties of composite materials constituents. The approach followed is to use the test data of UD composites at high strain rates to generate the respective high strain rate data of the constituent materials by inverse modelling using a micro scale finite element model as the forward problem. A strategic approach was adopted wherein a parametric study was performed to identify the sensitive parameters of the constituent materials for each case of loading. The objective of the inverse modelling problem considered in this study is to estimate these constituent material parameters through quadratic minimization of the objective function which is the sum of the squares of the residuals, based on the difference between experimental data and the model output. The micro scale model for each case of loading was then considered as an independent inverse problem to estimate these sensitive parameters. Numerical solvers from the optimization module of Scipy and NAG C library sub routines were used for parameter estimation based on their ability to estimate material parameters for non-linear least square problems. Python scripts were used to set up the problem to call the optimisation solver and also to interface with Abaqus FEA software for solving the forward problem for each iteration. Experimental data from Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) compression testing were used for generation of high strain rate data. The sensitivity of estimated parameters to errors in experimental data has also been studied. The role of a user defined Jacobian based on micromechanical theories for faster convergence and the issues involved in inverse modelling are also discussed in the paper. The properties generated are intended to provide valuable information for impact response simulation of composite parts subjected to high velocity/ballistic impact.

1 INTRODUCTION

Virtual testing of structural composites has gained considerable recognition in the last decade, as there has been a trend of increased availability of high performance computers and computational software at affordable cost. One of the approaches that has been followed in virtual testing is the use of multi scale models for understanding the mechanical behaviour of components [1, 2]. In order to achieve this, a multi-scale modelling environment was developed by Lidgett et al. [3-5] for prediction of high strain rate properties with the objective of using the properties so generated for simulation of the behaviour of composite structures subjected to high velocity impact/ballistic loading. The multi-scale modelling approach followed in their study involved the prediction of lamina level properties from the constituent material properties at high strain rates using micro scale models. The properties obtained for the lamina were used as input for the prediction of the properties for laminates. The micro scale models used for generation of the lamina properties had extensive material models for fibres, interfaces and matrices for prediction of lamina level characteristics at high strain rates. This paper discusses an approach of using these micro scale models as a forward problem in inverse modelling to estimate the high strain rate properties of the composite material constituents.

Various researchers have used the inverse method for estimating material properties/parameters with finite element models (commonly known as Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) technique). Kajberg et al. [6] estimated viscoelastic parameters of an elastic-viscoelastic material model proposed by Perzyna [7]. They simulated a high strain rate event through inverse methods by comparison of repeated FE model results with the deformation pattern obtained from microscopic high speed photography of the event. The parameters were estimated for tensile testing of mild steel at strain rates over 10^4 s^{-1} . The deformation data were recorded with a high speed camera in 15 frames with an exposure time of $0.4 \mu\text{s}$ and frame interval of $2 \mu\text{s}$. The effect of uncertainty in the measurement was also studied based on a sensitivity analysis. Since the inertia forces were insignificant compared to the measured force, static conditions were assumed in the FE analysis for simplicity. The simulation of the experiment with estimated parameters showed close agreement with the experimental results. Sztefek and Olsson [8] used an inverse method for evaluating the compressive stiffness reduction at the region of damage in the composite laminates subjected to impact. Optically measured displacement fields (from DIC) were obtained from the test and fed to an FE model which performs an iterative update of the material properties to match the predicted displacement with the actual test data. The objective of the inverse method was to minimize the difference between the measured and computed in plane components of the displacement fields. Sztefek and Olsson [9] also used a similar approach for evaluating the tensile stiffness reduction at the region of damage in composite laminates subjected to impact. Rahmani et al. [10] also developed a hybrid optimization procedure for inverse identification of mechanical properties of composite materials. The hybrid optimisation procedure uses the initial solution from a genetic algorithm or a direct search algorithm as the initial guess value for the gradient based search algorithms. This type of hybridisation of optimising procedure helps in better global searching and high convergence rate to the desired solution. Also, regularization is achieved by imposing constraints upon the minimisation problem so that predicted properties from a micromechanical model match with those obtained from experimental measurements. Markiewicz et al. [11] used an inverse approach to establish elastic-plastic and viscoelastic model parameters for the Cowper-Symonds constitutive model, from data obtained from quasi static and dynamic axial crushing of thin walled tubes. The parameters were estimated using the Pam-Opt mathematical optimisation solver and the numerical solution was carried out through Pam-Crash. The parameters thus obtained were used for simulating the dynamic 3 point bending impact using Pam-Crash and the results showed good correlation with the actual experiment. It can be observed that the various researchers have successfully used inverse models for estimation of material properties for various engineering problems. Depending on the type of the problem, different types of algorithm have been used. However, none of the published literature discusses compression property or transverse property estimation of composite fibres at high strain rates.

This paper describes the use of the finite element method updating technique for inverse estimation of high strain properties of composite constituents. A brief overview of the micro mechanical model used for inverse modelling as the forward problem is included. The paper also highlights the results of the parametric study carried out for identification of the sensitive parameters to be estimated/evaluated from the inverse modelling/actual testing.

2 MICRO SCALE MODEL FOR PREDICTION OF HIGH STRAIN RATE PROPERTIES OF UD COMPOSITE LAMINA

The micro scale finite element model developed by Lidgett [5] is a hexagonal closed packed arranged unit cell which comprises of fibre with interface embedded in matrix material (Fig. 1). The interfacial layer is very thin and assumed to be one tenth of the fibre radius. To ensure that each unit cell has the same deformation mode with no separation and no overlap, periodic boundary conditions were applied to the faces, edges and corners through linear constraint equations [5]. For the material model, fibres are assumed to be transversely isotropic and elastic until failure whereas the matrix is assumed to be isotropic and elastic until failure. The fibre is considered to be strain rate insensitive and the matrix was considered as strain rate sensitive in the material model used. Hence, strain rate scaling constants are required for the matrix for both stiffness and strength as defined in the logarithmic equation (1).

$$A_{RT} = A_0 \left[1 + C_A \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_0} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where, A_{RT} : Rate Adjusted property
 A_0 : Quasi-Static Value
 C_A : Strain Rate Scaling Constant
 $\dot{\epsilon}_0, \dot{\epsilon}$: Reference and Actual Strain Rate

The maximum stress criterion was used for element deletion for fibre failure and for damage evolution in the matrix. The interface is assumed to have the same property as that of the matrix, however different strain rate scaling constants were used for the stiffness and interfacial shear strength. The failure of the interface is dictated by the shear stress along the interface in the longitudinal fibre direction which results in element deletion for further time increments. A user defined sub routine was written in Fortran based on material characteristics described above for all the micro scale constituents. The dummy nodes which are linked to the faces, edges and corners of the unit cell through a linear constraint equation were used for the application of displacement. Based on the desired strain rate, the rate of loading applied to the dummy nodes was varied. The micro scale finite element model and user defined sub routine were developed [5] for implementation in the Abaqus/Explicit FEA package.

Fig. 1 Hexagonal closed packed unit cell used for micro scale models and the definition of each face, edges and corners [4]

3 INVERSE MODELLING PROCEDURE

The main objective of an inverse problem is to determine n model parameters from a set of m measurements, where $m \geq n$, which can be represented by equation (2) as given below

$$F(\beta) = d \quad (2)$$

Where F represents the governing equations based on the physics of the problem, relating the β (the column vector consisting of n model parameters) to the measured data d which consists of m measurements. An objective function (r_i) which compares a predicted quantity from a numerical model with the test data would be generated for each function call for each data point. The optimisation solver then estimates the parameter through the quadratic minimization of the non-linear square problem (equations (3) and (4)), which minimises the function S which is the sum of the squares of the residuals, r_i . In equation (4), y_i is the data measurement which is dependent on the input

parameters (x_i) and β , the column vector consisting of n model parameters that are to be estimated from the inverse problem.

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^m r_i^2 \quad (3)$$

where,
$$r_i = y_i - f(x_i, \beta) \quad (4)$$

The procedure followed for inverse modelling in this study is summarised in the flowchart shown in Fig 2. In the inverse problem considered here, the micro mechanical model described above is defined as the forward problem, where the definition of the objective function is based on comparing the stress observed in the experiment to the stress level predicted by the model for a given strain for a specified loading rate and loading type. The stress-strain characteristics are generated through analysis of the micro scale finite element model. The stress observed is compared with the interpolated/extrapolated experimental data and expressed as a residual as represented in equation (4). The residual is evaluated for each data point and thus will result in an over determined system of equations. The solution is obtained by performing a numerical optimisation which minimises the objective function as defined in equation (3). The function tolerance and solution tolerance are specified to cause exit from the optimisation solver once the solution converges.

Fig. 2 Flowchart describing the methodology followed for inverse modelling

Depending upon the parameters to be estimated, the respective micro scale model is chosen and the inverse problem is defined. The optimisation solvers, from Scipy and the NAG C library were used for constituent parameter estimation for which Python scripts were written to call the respective solver. These were interfaced with Abaqus to evaluate the objective function for each iteration. The solver 'leastsq' available in the module 'optimize' in Scipy is a solver based on the Levenberg-Markquardt algorithm [12, 13] whereas the NAG solver (e04unc) minimises the arbitrary smooth sum of squares function using a sequential quadratic programming(SQP) method [14]. The optimisation involving 'leastsq' solver were efficiently carried on 64 bit Abaqus versions along with compatible 64 bit version of Numpy and Scipy. The optimisation with e04unc used NAG C library (CLL6A23DHL-Mark 23) along with its necessary nag4py installations inside the Python environment of Abaqus 6.14.1. It was observed that an optimisation run involving the micro scale FE model performed in 64 bit Abaqus, using a Intel Xeon E5 2670 2.60 GHz processor with 32GB RAM, took 22 hours. The

time taken was further reduced by employing mass scaling options and increasing the loading rate. In such cases, the scaling constants were appropriately modified to nullify the effect of loading rate on mechanical characteristics.

3 PARAMETRIC STUDIES FOR IDENTIFICATION OF SENSITIVE PARAMETERS

The material model defined in the user sub routine for the micro scale model, developed by Lidgett [5], requires around 40 material parameters to be given as input parameters inside the Abaqus input file for the user sub routine. These input material parameters include basic material properties of the fibre, the matrix, the matrix strain rate scaling constants and damage parameters. Since inverse problems are ill posed, it is desirable to identify the parameters that strongly affect the composite characteristics for a given loading condition. Hence, a parametric study was conducted on the micro scale model, to identify the sensitive parameters for each loading condition. These parameters will then be used in the inverse problem.

The parametric study was carried out to assess the sensitivity of 23 independent material parameters defined in the material user sub routines used for the micro scale models for a rate of loading corresponding to strain rate of 10^4 s^{-1} . The parametric study was performed for all cases of loading (tension, compression and shear in longitudinal and transverse directions). The parameters influencing the stiffness and strength of the composite were identified for each case of loading. Table 1 shows the sensitive parameters identified for each case of loading and their extent of influence in composite stiffness and strength when the parameters were varied by ± 20 percent of the base value.

Loading Type	Sensitive Parameters	Stiffness		Strength	
		20%	-20%	20%	-20%
Longitudinal Tension(Z)	Longitudinal Fibre Modulus	19.8	-19.8	-5.5	-3
	Longitudinal Fibre Tensile Strength	0	0	20.9	-21.1
Longitudinal Compression(Z)	Longitudinal Fibre Modulus	19.8	-19.8	2.6	-8.3
	Longitudinal Fibre Compression Strength	0	0	14.5	-28.8
Transverse Tension(X)	Matrix Modulus	9.6	-10.7	-0.4	0.5
	Transverse Fibre Modulus	8.9	-11.1	0.6	-0.7
	Matrix Poisson's ratio	6.9	-3.8	18.1	-7.7
	Matrix Tension Strength	0	0	19.6	-19.8
Transverse Tension(Y)	Matrix Modulus	8.8	-11.7	-2	2.3
	Transverse Fibre Modulus	8.2	-10.7	1.6	-2.2
	Matrix Poisson's ratio	5.5	-5.1	25.8	-12
	Matrix Tension Strength	0	0	20.2	-20.2
Transverse Compression(X)	Matrix Modulus	9.5	-10.7	1.2	-1.5
	Transverse Fibre Modulus	9.2	-10.8	-0.8	1.3
	Matrix Poisson's ratio	6.9	-3.8	30.7	-13.2
	Matrix Compression Strength	0	0	19.7	-19.8
Transverse Compression(Y)	Matrix Modulus	8.7	-11.9	-1.2	1.2
	Transverse Fibre Modulus	8.8	-11.7	0.9	-1.2
	Matrix Poisson's ratio	5.4	-5.1	18.5	-11
	Matrix Compression Strength	0	0	20.1	-20
Transverse Shear (XY)	Matrix Modulus	7.9	-11	-3.5	3.4
	Fibre Shear Modulus (G12)	13	-9.2	1.1	-0.9
	Matrix Poisson's ratio	-1.8	2.8	14.1	-8.2
	Matrix Shear Strength	0	0	20	-20.9
Longitudinal Shear (XZ)	Matrix Modulus	13.1	-14.8	-2.1	-3
	Fibre Shear Modulus (G13)	5.3	-7	-1.5	-1
	Matrix Poisson's ratio	-3.1	3.9	-3.4	-3.3
	Matrix Shear Strength	0	0	0	37.4
	Interfacial Shear Strength	0	0	73.5	-20

Table 1 Variation of Composite Stiffness and Strength for $\pm 20\%$ change in sensitive parameters

4 INVERSE MODELLING ESTIMATION OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS

4.1 Estimation of Constituent Parameters from Composite Longitudinal Compression Characteristics

The parametric study to understand the sensitivity of the material parameters shows that longitudinal composite stiffness is primarily controlled by variation in fibre stiffness in both tension and compression. Longitudinal composite strength is predominantly controlled by fibre strength and fibre stiffness (Table 1). Data available in the literature on IM7-8552 [15] for longitudinal compression testing were used for estimation of the longitudinal fibre compression modulus and strength. The inverse modelling estimation of longitudinal compressive fibre stiffness for various strain rates shows consistent results with different solvers, as shown in Table 2. The small variation in the estimated values for different guesses can be related to solver exit criteria, where little difference exists between the objective function and the estimated parameter predicted for successive iterations. Even though consistent estimation was achieved with different initial guess values, it should be noted that a different value could be estimated for certain initial guess values contrary to the expected value. Such anomalies in estimation can be related to the optimisation solver locating a local minimum in the experimental curve. This can be avoided by curve fitting the experimental data before its evaluation in the objective function. Hence, an additional step of curve fitting was introduced for estimation of the fibre compression strength and it showed a consistent estimation for various guess values for the NAG solver (e04unc). However, the compressive fibre estimation using the Scipy solver failed to estimate a value different from the guess value for the same objective function as defined for the same problem attempted with the NAG solver. The estimated values for quasi-static fibre stiffness and strength are 192 GPa and 1.52 GPa and for dynamic fibre stiffness and strength are 239 GPa and 2.58 GPa respectively. Fig. 3 shows the close prediction of the micro model with the experimental data using inverse modelling derived constituent properties. In general, this close prediction validates the micro mechanical material model and also the inverse methodology approach for predicting parameters. The results also show strain rate sensitivity for both longitudinal fibre stiffness and longitudinal fibre strength. The matrix scaling constants used were derived from the published strain rate data for the epoxy resin [13] rather than 8552 resin data. Moreover, it should be noted that the accuracy of the estimated results is very much dependent on the accuracy of the test data and the effectiveness of the test method to predict actual compression stiffness and strength of the composite. This can particularly be the case for compression strength, where low values have been reported [16] due to delamination and other unintended failure mechanisms such as end crushing, transverse splitting etc. In such a case, the estimated strength values for the fibre will tend to be an underestimate and the data needs to be used with care in design and simulations.

Strain Rate(s^{-1})	Estimated Compressive Fibre Stiffness(GPa)						Estimated Compressive Fibre Strength (GPa)					
	Guess 1 = 30		Guess 2 = 200		Guess 3 = 270		Guess 1 =1		Guess 2 = 3		Guess 3 =5	
	Scipy	NAG	Scipy	NAG	Scipy	NAG	Scipy	NAG	Scipy	NAG	Scipy	NAG
1 e-4	192.08	190.35	192.67	192.37	193.01	192.16	1	1.52	3	1.52	5	1.52
93	239.39	239.38	238.43	239.54	239.16	239.22	1	2.58	3	2.58	5	2.58

Table 2 Estimated Longitudinal Parameters with different solvers (for different guess values and different strain rates)

Fig. 3 Comparison of Experimental data [15] for Longitudinal Compression with micro mechanical prediction based on inverse estimated fibre data for quasi-static and high strain rate

4.1.2 Effect of Noisy Data

The data used for estimation of the longitudinal strength were also perturbed with a random variation of up to 5 percent for each data point for both the stress and strain values. The noisy data were then used for the estimation of constituent material parameters. Table 3 shows the results for the estimation of longitudinal fibre compression modulus with and without the noisy data shows less than a 0.5 percent variation in the estimated parameter.

Longitudinal Compression Modulus Estimation(GPa)				
Guess Value	Scipy With Jacobian		NAG	
	Actual Data	5% Variation	Actual Data	5% Variation
30	192.08	193.84	190.35	191.42
200	192.67	193.64	192.37	193.38
270	193.01	193.58	192.16	193.09

Table 3 Prediction of Longitudinal Compression Modulus with noisy data

4.1.3 Effect of a User Defined Jacobian

A user defined Jacobian was introduced to the inverse modelling problem based on the rule of mixtures relationship available from the theory of micromechanics [17]. For example, in the longitudinal compression problem, the approximate Jacobian definition is given in equation (5).

$$\sigma = E_f \varepsilon_f V_f + E_m \varepsilon_m V_m \quad (5)$$

where, σ is the composite strength,
 E is the Fibre Modulus,
 ε is the composite strain and
 V is the Volume fraction

The subscripts f,m denote the fibre and matrix respectively.

It can be seen that the introduction of the user defined Jacobian results in a reduction in the number of iterations required to arrive at the final solution (Table 4). Also, the NAG solver was able to estimate the predicted value significantly faster compared to the Scipy solver. One of the reasons for

the requirement of a large number of calls to Scipy is that the Jacobian definition is made as a separate function in Scipy, whereas in NAG, a single call can give information on the objective function and the Jacobian. Another reason for the increased calls in Scipy is the tolerance definition followed for the optimisation exit criteria. Since the NAG solver (e04unc) has proven to be faster, it was decided to use this solver for further property estimation.

Longitudinal Fibre Compression Modulus (GPa)			
Guess Value	Scipy Without Jacobian (No. of Calls)	Scipy With Jacobian (No. of Calls)	NAG With Jacobian (No. of Calls)
30	190.39(26)	192.08(26)	190.35(4)
200	196.86(28)	192.67(18)	192.37(2)
270	194.89(35)	193.01(29)	192.16(4)

Table 4 Quasi-Static Longitudinal Fibre Compression Modulus Estimation with and without Jacobian

4.1.4 Use of Constrained Optimization Solvers

One of the issues in interfacing Abaqus with an unconstrained optimization solver is that the solver can give a value unacceptable for Abaqus to solve which can result in abrupt termination of the optimization routine and incorrect parameter prediction. For example, a negative value for the modulus or a value greater than 0.5 for Poisson's ratio for an isotropic material can result in errors in the Abaqus analysis. To avoid this, defining bounds or defining specific constraints (linear and non-linear) on the parameters can help. Hence, a constrained optimisation feature of the NAG solver (e04unc) was used in estimation of the longitudinal fibre compression strength. In this case, specific bounds were set for the parameters and this approach was observed to be successful for accurate estimation of fibre strength (Table 2).

4.2 ESTIMATION OF CONSTITUENT PARAMETERS FROM COMPOSITE TRANSVERSE COMPRESSION CHARACTERISTICS

The stress-strain curve for transverse compression shows a linear elastic region followed by gradual yielding and then failure of the composite. From the parametric study (Table 1), it is seen that transverse compressive stiffness is influenced by matrix modulus, transverse fibre modulus and the matrix Poisson's ratio. On the other hand, transverse compressive strength is influenced primarily by matrix compressive strength and matrix Poisson's ratio. Since transverse compression modulus is influenced by more than one parameter, it is important to assign a value to one of the material parameters and to predict the other parameter through an inverse approach. This is required as both parameters tend to influence the resulting composite modulus equally, and it would not be mathematically possible to estimate two parameters from a single linear equation. Similar to estimation of parameters from longitudinal characteristics, the inverse problem was therefore set up to predict the transverse fibre modulus and matrix compression strength from the transverse compression data of UD composites as two independent single parameter problem. The experimental data required for inverse modelling was generated by performing mechanical testing, under transverse loading conditions, on unidirectional laminated composites made from Hexply[®] IM7-8552. The quasi-static characteristics were obtained through testing UD composite specimens on a standard INSTRON 50 kN UTM at a constant displacement rate of 0.25mm/min whereas dynamic transverse compression strength were obtained from Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar compression testing performed on the unidirectional specimens in the transverse direction at strain rates around 2000 s⁻¹. Since the specimens are subjected to end loading for the high rate SHPB tests, the same specimen dimension and same testing procedure were followed for quasi-static tests. The approximate relationship for transverse modulus as formulated by Chamis [18] was used for definition of the Jacobian. For the estimation of the transverse fibre modulus, the linear region of the experimental curve and the

predicted stress strain characteristics were compared. The estimation of the transverse fibre modulus shows consistent values for different initial guess values. The matrix compression strength was evaluated by comparing the experimental and predicted characteristics curve for the entire loading region. Even though the estimated matrix compressive strength was higher compared to other epoxy resins, there is consistency in its estimation for different initial guess values. The quasi static transverse fibre modulus and matrix compression strength predicted using the inverse modelling approach is 6.9 GPa and 213 MPa respectively (Table 5). The same approach was used to estimate the parameters from the high strain transverse compression characteristics. The transverse fibre stiffness estimated shows significantly higher value compared to its quasi-static value. Similar to the strain rate sensitivity observed for longitudinal parameters, the strain rate sensitivity needs to be verified with the actual data for 8552 epoxy resin. The material model definition in the user subroutine defines the strength characteristics of the matrix through the quasi static compression strength and the strain rate scaling constants for matrix strength for each loading type. Hence, instead of estimation of the matrix compression strength at higher strain rate, the high strain rate transverse compression characteristics were used for estimation of the matrix compressive strength scaling constant which has been defined in the user sub routine for the micro scale models based on equation (1). The estimation of strength scaling constant was attempted using the loading region of the high strain rate transverse compression characteristics. The estimated strength scaling constant was lower compared (Table 6) to the scaling constants derived of Epon epoxy resins published in the literature [19].

Strain Rate(/s)	Transverse Fibre Stiffness (GPa)			Matrix Compression Strength (GPa)		
	Guess 1 =3	Guess 2 = 7	Guess 3 = 18	Guess 1 =0.1	Guess 2 = 0.2	Guess 3 = 0.3
1 e-4	6.9	6.86	6.9	0.213	0.212	0.21

Table 5 Estimated Constituent Parameters with Quasi Static Transverse Compression Data

Strain Rate(/s)	Transverse Compressive Fibre Stiffness (GPa)			Matrix Strength Scaling Constant		
	Guess 1 =3	Guess 2 = 7	Guess 3 = 18	Guess1=0.05	Guess2=0.08	Guess 3 = 0.16
2000	16.94	16.94	16.91	0.029	0.03	0.03

Table 6 Estimated Constituent Parameters with High Strain Rate (2000/s) Transverse Compression Data

Fig. 4 Comparison of Experimental data for Transverse Compression with micro mechanical prediction based on inverse estimated constituent data for quasi-static and high strain rate

The estimated values were then used for prediction of the high strain rate transverse compression characteristics of the carbon epoxy composites showing good agreement with the experimental characteristic curves obtained from the testing (Fig. 4). For high strain rate testing, the disintegration of composites was observed during the initial loading phase. This disintegration of the composites during transverse compression can be attributed to the comparatively higher void content (around 2 percent) in the composites. This is likely to be the reason for the discrepancy between the simulation and experimental high strain rate curves shown in Fig. 4.

4.3 ESTIMATION OF CONSTITUENT PARAMETERS THROUGH SIMULTANEOUS TWO PARAMETER INVERSE ESTIMATION

The inverse problem has also been set up to estimate the matrix compressive strength and the transverse fibre modulus simultaneously from the transverse compression data of a UD composite using a two parameter analysis. The attempt to estimate both the parameters simultaneously was unsuccessful as it could not converge to a constant value for different initial guess values as can be seen from the results shown in Table 7 and needs to be further investigated. The specific bounds were set for the above parameters for the inverse problem considered. The failure of the optimisation solver to estimate accurately the two parameters can be related to the fact that both the parameters that were attempted to be estimated were uncoupled parameters which have its own region of influence in the stress strain characteristics. The matrix compression strength does not have any influence on the transverse compression modulus of the composite and the extent of sensitivity of transverse fibre modulus on transverse compression strength of the composite is much lower compared to the matrix compression as could be seen from the parametric study (Table 1).

Transverse Compressive Fibre Stiffness (GPa), Matrix Compressive Strength (GPa)					
Guess 1 = 12, 0.1		Guess 2 = 5, 0.25		Guess 3 = 20, 0.12	
11.05	0.09	16.97	0.257	13.63	0.115

Table 7 Estimation of Transverse Fibre Modulus and Matrix Compressive Strength for different guess values with the NAG solver using simultaneous two parameter estimation

5 CONCLUSIONS

An inverse modelling methodology for prediction of composite material constituents using micro mechanical models has been successfully developed. The prediction of the constituent longitudinal parameters (both compression modulus and strength) was consistent for different guess values using the NAG solver (e04unc). The transverse fibre compression modulus and matrix compression strength were estimated with the quasi static compression data successfully. The NAG solver was found to be more efficient compared to a Scipy solver (leastsq) in this application. It has also been found to be advisable to use a user defined Jacobian for faster prediction of the material parameters wherever possible. The estimated fibre properties showed strain rate sensitivity, however the effect of rate sensitivity needs to be verified with 8552 resin data. A constrained optimization solver was employed for use in strength prediction where defining the bounds of the parameters helped in convergence. The inverse modelling approach for estimation of more than one parameter from a single model is still under investigation.

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